

The visible spectra of the complex in water reveal absorption maxima at 640 (strong), 598, 478, 464 and 452 nm. Strong absorptions around 600 nm have been previously noticed for η^5 -(C₅H₅)₃UCl¹⁰ and several other uranium(IV) complexes¹¹. The presence of uranium(IV) in the complex is thus indicated. Owing to the insolubility of the complex in the common solvents we could neither get the conductivity and nmr data nor determine its molecular weight employing the usual methods.

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Characterisation of a New Complex of S₄N₄H₄ (TSTI) with ZrOCl₂ by XRD Spectrum

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SURVEY of literature reveals that complexes of TSTI (S₄N₄H₄)^{1,2}, except with silver³ have not been synthesised and studied so far. Therefore, the complex of TSTI with ZrOCl₂ was prepared and the results of investigations are reported here.

Experimental

TSTI (S₄N₄H₄) was prepared by methanolic SnCl₂ reduction⁴ of S₄N₄. The formation of TSTI was established by its m.p., molecular weight, ir and electronic spectra. The complex of TSTI with ZrOCl₂ (anhydrous) was synthesised by

refluxing equimolar amount of TSTI and ZrOCl₂ (anhydrous) in DMF for ~48 h with constant mechanical stirring. The resulting light brown product was separated, washed with DMF to free it from unreacted TSTI and ZrOCl₂, and then dried in vacuum.

The complex was analysed using gravimetric and absorption spectral techniques⁶. Its molecular weight was determined by viscosity method. Ir (KBr) and electronic (reflectance) spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 337 and VSU-22 spectrophotometers, respectively, at 300 K. X-Ray powder diffraction spectra were recorded on a XRD-6 GM-11 diffractometer using CuK_α (λ 1.5418 Å) as a source of radiation.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data of the complex (Found : Zr, 25.0 ; N, 15.0 ; H, 1.1 ; Cl, 19.6 ; O, 4.3%) and molecular weight 1135, lead to the molecular formula of the complex as (S₄N₄H₄.ZrOCl₂)₃. It has m.p. 228°, and its colour darkens.

On the basis of available literature, its ir spectrum is interpreted and compared to that of TSTI and strong absorption bands at 719s and 765s cm⁻¹ due to two free S-N vibrations and two other frequencies at 1 110 and 1 162 cm⁻¹ (shifted to higher region), indicate the presence of two S-N bands having coordinated nitrogen. The peaks at 1 370-1 605 cm⁻¹ correspond to N-H bands. The broad band at 2 885-3 420 cm⁻¹ is due to δ_{NH} showing hydrogen bonding between N atom of S₄N₄H₄ and Cl atom of ZrOCl₂. The ir spectra clearly indicate that S₄N₄H₄ is linked to ZrOCl₂ by bidentate bridging of Zr atom through coordination by N terminals of S₄N₄H₄ ring, forming a coordinated trimer (Fig. 1).

Further, its electronic spectra reveal three peaks at 360, 300 and 289 nm. The peak at 289 nm is due to charge transfer transition in ZrOCl₂ caused by its electrovalent character. The presence of charge transfer transition is also supported by the ratio ν₃/ν₂=0.83 (<1). The value calculated for the oscillator strength (f=1.12×10⁻⁴), suggests that the 360 and 300 nm transitions are spin-allowed laporte forbidden transition. The values determined from its electronic spectrum, for the band gap energy (ΔE 0.69 eV) and conductivity (λ_c=3.2×10⁻¹² Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹) indicate the semiconductive nature of the complex which may be due to the presence of holes in its internal array.

To arrive at conclusive geometrical structure of the complex, Miller indices I/I₀ and d(Å) are calculated from its X-ray powder diffraction spectrum which is obtained over 2θ range 6-60°. The values of I/I₀ show a gradation supporting the presence of holes and semiconductivity of the complex and the fall in intensity suggests that complex is less crystalline. The d values which coincide

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Fig. 1. Structure of trimer complex $(S_4N_4H_4.ZrOCl_2)_3$.

with the calculated ones for various groups confirms the presence of free S-N,N coordinated S-N and N-H bands^v as indicated by the ir spectra. The axial ratios and axial angles computed as $a_0 = b_0 = 12.18 \text{ \AA}$, $c_0 = 24.36 \text{ \AA}$; $\alpha = \beta = 90^\circ$ and $\gamma = 120^\circ$, express the hexagonal geometrical structure of the complex (Fig. 1). The repeating of peaks and subsequently blurring of the spectra confirm the presence of various groups and trimer form of the complex.

TABLE 1—X-RAY POWDER DIFFRACTION PATTERN OF COMPLEX

2θ	(hkl)	d (Obs.) Å	d (Calcd.) Å	I/I_0
7.2	100	12.97	12.18	13.33
7.4	100	12.86	12.18	8.33
12.5	111	7.02	7.02	6.66
22.0	221	4.04	4.05	10.00
23.3	310	3.83	3.85	13.33
25.0	222	3.56	3.51	11.66
26.0	320	3.43	3.37	8.33
27.7	321	3.22	3.25	10.00
32.7	331	2.74	2.79	20.00
38.3	333	2.35	2.34	83.33
41.3	440	2.18	2.15	9.33
44.5	442	2.03	2.03	100.00
53.6	551	1.70	1.70	1.66
58.4	553	1.58	1.58	3.33

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Preparation and Characterisation of some 3d Metal Complexes with 2-Hydroxymaleianilic Acid and 2-Carboxymaleianilic Acid

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In this paper we report the preparation and characterisation of some 3d metal complexes of 2-hydroxymaleianilic and 2-carboxymaleianilic acids.

Experimental

2-Hydroxymaleianilic acid (OH-Ma) and 2-carboxymaleianilic acid (OC-Ma) were prepared^{1,2} by the condensation of maleic anhydride and *ortho*-substituted-aromatic amines.

All the other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade.

To an ethanolic solution (250 ml) of 0.02 M OH-Ma and OC-Ma, 0.25 M KOH was added with stirring until pH of the solution reached ≈ 8 . To it 0.02 M aqueous solution (250 ml) of the metal salts were mixed with stirring and digested over a water-bath for 1 h. The crystalline precipitates so obtained were filtered, washed several times with water and recrystallised. Chlorides of Mn^{II} , Fe^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , acetate of Cu^{II} and freshly prepared hydroxide of Cr^{III} were used for preparing the complexes.

Results of elemental analysis, molar conductance data of the complexes in dimethylformamide and magnetic moment values at 26° are stated in the